

Importance of Developing Economic and Protecting Environment

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Abstract: Corporate Social Responsibility is corporates works, for sustainable development. Corporates are no more judged on their financial parameters alone. Corporates lies as a part of society; thus it becomes corporate's responsibility. Responsibility activities to a corporate firm can be difficult to quantify and it has become dominant in business reporting. Corporate Social Responsibility is gaining more and more attraction towards business actions. India is the first economy across the globe to lay Corporate Social Responsibility in to law for certain companies who fulfill the criteria of the law (Sec 135 of Indian Companies Act 2013). The CSR concepts and background for companies to implement need which are directly proportional to CSR.

Index Terms – Corporate Social Responsibility, Social Development, Sustainable Development, Accountability.

I. INTRODUCTION:

Corporate Social Responsibility is a concept which believes that the corporates must integrate socio-environmental concerns into their business activities. It is signified by contribution sunder taken by corporates to society through its business activities and social investment. Corporate decision-making Process should not be based merely on financial factors such as profits /Dividends, considerable interest must be given for social and environmental factors and their consequences. In India, Corporate social responsibility has been seen traditionally as a charitable activity. And in keeping with the Indian convention, such activities were performed but not deliberated, which resulted in incomplete activities.

CSR rests on the ideology of give and take companies take resources in the form of raw material, human resources etc from the society by performing the task of CSR. The companies are giving something back to the society. CSR moved from social practices to an effective business tool.

India has the world's richest tradition of CSR. The term CSR may be relatively new to India but the dates back to the Mauryan history were philosopher's like Kautilya emphasized on ethical practices and principles while conducting the business. CSR has been informally practices in ancient times in form of charity to the poor and disadvantaged. CSR moved from a social practices to an effective business tool there are several globally recognized guidelines, frame work tools pertaining to CSR are available.

II. NEW COMPANIES ACT, 2013 – CSR PROVISIONS:

Companies Act 2013 has come up with a number of new provisions which changed the appearance of Indian Corporate Business. CSR is one of such new provisions included in the Companies Act 2013. CSR with the ideology of Give and Take. It will be curious to observe the ways in which this will translate into action at the ground level, and how the accepting of CSR is set to undergo a change⁴. Section 135 of the Companies Act 2013 gives the threshold limit for enforcement of the CSR 2% for the corporate:

- i. Net worth of the company to be Rs.500crore or more;
- ii. Turnover of the India's new ne Take, company to be Rs.1000crore or more;
- iii. Net profit of the company to be Rs.5crore or more. Further as per the CSR rules, the provisions of CSR are not only applicable to Indian corporate, but also applicable to branch and project offices of a foreign company in India.

In 1st July 2019 aimed the media buzz for some changes in the CSR rules after the recommendation of the high-powered committee on CSR (under the ministry of corporate affairs government of India). It can be a so thing news for India's social sector that India's companies will have to spend at most 11% more CSR fund in the current financial year (2019-2020) than what they had in 2018-19.

III. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

- i. To understand the CSR approaches by Indian Companies to CSR Provisions of Companies Act
- ii. To understand CSR Provisions as per "Schedule VII of The Companies Act, 2013."
- iii. To compare key CSR practices being practiced by Indian companies as per thematic priorities.
- iv. To Compare Actual CSR Spending and Prescribed in the first five financial years after enactment of The Companies Act, 2013.

IV. EVOLUTION OF CSR IN INDIA:

In India CSR is not a new concept, the ancient philosophers of Maryann emperor conducted the CSR informally practiced in the form of charity. Till 1850's the richest and wealthy business men shared some part of their wealth in the form of charity and lead a helping hand to the needy people. In the pre independence era, the pioneers of industrialization also supported the concept of CSR. In 1900, the industrialist families like Tata's, Birla's, Modi's, Godrej, Bajaj..promoted this concept by setting up charitable foundation education, health care institutions, and trusts for the community development. Gandhi urged to powerful industrialist to share their wealth for benefit of underprivileged section of the society.

After 1980's CSR was influenced by the emergence of public sector undertaking to ensure proper distribution of wealth. Indian companies integrated CSR into a sustainable business strategy with globalization and economic liberalization in 1990's and partial withdrawal of controls and licensing system their wages the boom in the economic growth of the country.

V. NEED OF THE STUDY:

CSR is a vehicle through which organizations give something back to the general public. However, the test before the organizations is to distinguish CSR needs and the zones of creation which are significant with regards to society advancement. In this way, there is a need to think about and comprehend the CSR works on being taken by various corporate houses.

To make a general investigation that to what degree the Companies in India are doing CSR Activities to be in tune with CSR Provisions of Companies Act 2013, there is a need to investigate CSR Practices among companies in India.

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This is an exploratory research. The main source of Data is 'Secondary' and keeping in mind the objectives of the study the methodology is descriptive in nature. To ensure greater accuracy and in-depth analysis, the data are confined to secondary sources.

VII. SOURCES OF DATA:

Published Annual Reports, CSR Reports, official websites, Reports Published by Ministry of Corporate Affairs, Govt. of India and reports of surveys by private institutions.

VIII. PERIOD OF STUDY:

This study examines the CSR Spending in India in the first two financial years after the enactment of the Companies Act - 2013. i.e., Financial Year 2014-15 and 2018-19.

IX. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

The Data collected is arranged and analyses in a systematic and understandable manner as follows with the help of Tabulation.

Table 1:**Actual CSR and Prescribed CSR spending by Indian Companies from 2014-15 to 2018-19**

Year	Actual CSR spending	Prescribed CSR spending	Actual CSR Spending as a % of Prescribed CSR
2014-15	10065.93	17140.42	58.73
2015-16	14503.65	17044.45	85.09
2016-17	14312.03	19789.90	72.32
2017-18	13326.69	23247.90	57.32
2018-19	17548.63	25806.82	68.00

Analysis:

It is observed that Actual CSR Spending by the Indian Companies has an increasing trend during the study period of five years I.e., 2014-15 to 2018-19. However, Actual CSR Spending as a percentage of Prescribed CSR has a decreasing trend.

Table 2:
Number of Indian Companies for CSR Expenditure
vis-à-vis CSR Prescribed Amount

Year	More than prescribed amount of CSR	Equal to prescribed amount of CSR	Less than prescribed amount of CSR	Zero expenditure
2014-15	1611	1090	1983	5734
2015-16	3073	1336	3074	5472
2016-17	3642	1845	3318	4377
2017-18	4103	992	3130	3359

Analysis:

It is observed from the above table and graph that Number of Companies Spending more than the prescribed has an increasing trend during the study period and the number of companies with zero expenditures has decreased significantly over five years indicating positive movement towards compliance of CSR Provisions of New Companies Act – 2013.

Table 3:
Indian Companies Reported CSR Policy and CSR Commitment in their annual reports.

Year	Yes	No	Not Reported / Blank
2014-15	5086	955	10507
2015-16	7023	928	10339
2016-17	5666	426	13440
2017-18	6326	693	14318

Analysis:

It is observed from the above table and graph that Number of Companies reporting their CSR Policies in their annual reports has increased over the study period. However, Number Of Companies Not Reported/ Blank needs to improve their performance in setting up CSR Policy and communicating the same to the Stake Holders.

Table 4:
Implementation of CSR Projects by Indian Companies

Year	By non-profit arm of company	Directly by company	Government Body/ Agency	Implementing Agency (NGOs, Trusts, Societies, etc.)	Not Mentioned
2014-15	1105	7985	359	5643	13892
2015-16	1441	13925	760	9904	15288
2016-17	2155	19597	915	13855	12561
2017-18	2136	17718	935	12943	11073

Analysis:

It is observed from the above table and graph that Number of Companies implementing directly by themselves and through Implementing Agency (NGOs, Trusts and Societies) has an increasing trend indicating that the companies in India started involving more into giving back the society within which they operate.

Table 5:
Theme wise corporate social responsibility activities (INR Cr.)

Thematic priorities	Year			
	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18
Education, Differently Aabled, Livelihood	3188	4916	5545	5645
Encouraging Sports	58	139	180	225
Environmental Sustainability & Animal Welfare	859	1004	1342	1349
Gender Equality & Women Empowerment	190	342	468	484
Heritage Art and Culture	117	119	306	283
Not Mentioned	1338	1051	389	1
Other Sectors (Technology Incubator, Armed Forces, Admin Overheads)	10	37	61	41
PM National Relief Fund + Any other Fund	505	552	577	403
Poverty Alleviation, Healthcare & WASH	2640	4953	3841	3412
Rural Development	1059	1376	1552	1456
Slum Area Development	101	14	51	31
Total	10065	14503	14312	13330

Table 6:
CSR Funding in the Central Government Funds

Year	PM National Relief Fund	SwachhBharathKosh	Clean Ganga Fund	Any Other Funds	Total
2014-15	228.18	113.386	5.47	277.1	624.136
2015-16	218.04	325.52	32.82	334.35	910.73
2016-17	158.8	184.06	24.37	418.29	785.52
2017-18	152.26	211.57	4.44	250.52	618.79

Analysis:

It is observed from the above table and graph that there is no particular trend in CSR Funding in the Central Govt. Funds however PM National Relief Fund and SwachhBharathKosh have received maximum funds from Indian Companies through CSR Funds

X. CONCLUSION:

The basic objective of CSR in these days is to maximize the company's overall impact on the society and stakeholders. CSR policies, practices and programs are being comprehensively integrated by an increasing number of companies throughout their business operations and processes. A growing number of corporates feel that CSR is not just another form of indirect expense but is important for protecting the goodwill and reputation, defending attacks and increasing business competitiveness

Companies in India have been quite sensible in taking up CSR initiatives and integrating them in their business processes. It has become progressively projected in the Indian corporate setting because organizations have recognized that besides growing their businesses, it is also important to shape responsible and supportable relationships with the community at large. Companies now have specific departments and teams that develop specific policies, strategies and goals for their CSR programs and set separate budgets to support them.

The Level of CSR Giving in India will surely increase with the policies and provisions of "The Companies Act 2013.", New CSR Provisions will act as Game Changer for CSR in India. Companies have taken CSR reporting more serious as it is observed that quality and accessibility of CSR activities has improved a lot after enactment of New Companies Act, 2013.

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